

Article

Epidemiological Study of Injuries in the Spanish Men's Senior National Rugby XV Team

Cristian Solís-Mencía ¹, Elena Jiménez-Herranz ² , Mary Fiona McFall ³,
Mikel Aramberri Gutiérrez ⁴, Pablo García-Fernández ⁵

¹ Department of Medicine, Faculty of Health Sciences, University of Deusto, 48007 Bilbao, Spain; c.solis@deusto.es

² School of Sport Medicine, Department of Radiology, Rehabilitation and Physiotherapy, Faculty of Medicine, Complutense University Madrid, 28040 Madrid, Spain; mariaelj@ucm.es (E.J.-H.); jjramosa@ucm.es (J.J.R.-Á.)

³ Health Faculty, Camilo Jose Cela University, 28692 Madrid, Spain; mmcfall@ucj.edu

⁴ Alai Sports Medicine Clinic, 28055 Madrid, Spain; aramberri@centroalai.es

⁵ Department of Radiology, Rehabilitation and Physiotherapy, Faculty of Nursing, Physiotherapy and Podiatry, Complutense University Madrid, 28692 Madrid, Spain; pablga25@ucm.es

* Correspondence: jjmontoy@ucm.es; Tel.: +34-913941218

Abstract: (1) Background: Due to the risk factors involved and the special characteristics of the game, rugby players are reported to have elevated levels of injury. The aim of this longitudinal prospective cohort study with a 2b level of evidence is to investigate the incidence of injury in the Spanish Men's Senior National Rugby XV team, identify the most frequent injury types, and the game actions that cause them. (2) Methods: we studied a total of 72 players from the Spanish Men's Senior National Rugby XV team while they played the Nation's Cup for four consecutive seasons. We recorded all the injuries occurring both during games and training sessions, according to World Rugby consensus. (3) Results: Out of a total of 27 injuries, the higher incidence was during the matches as opposed to the training sessions (100.0 [95% CI: 62.0–132.9] per 1000 player hours (ph) and 1.17 [95% CI: 0–2.5] per 1000 ph during matches and training, respectively). The most common injuries were muscular injuries (41.6 [95% CI: 16.3–66.9] per 1000 ph) and concussion (29.1 [95% CI: 7.8–50.4] per 1000 ph). Tackling caused more injuries (50.0 [95% CI: 22.4–77.5] per 1000 ph). (4) Conclusions: Muscular injuries and concussion are the most common, 28% of concussion cases are diagnosed after the match, and tackling is the game action causing most of these injuries, with a higher incidence in players who play the whole match.

Keywords: rugby; injury; concussion; epidemiology

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1. Introduction

Rugby Union is an intermittent sport which is distinguished by frequent impact and the application of high force [1]. It also holds one of the highest incidences of injury for a professional sport [2]. However, this incidence is lower in amateur rugby than in professional rugby [3–9]. It has been shown to be affected by age and level of play, and to be higher during actual rugby matches [10,11]. This growth may be negatively impacted by the consequences of these frequent injuries [12]. Each injury makes it impossible for the player to continue training and thus competing. Both the injured professional and injured amateur rugby player miss an average of 20.7 days to 37.4 days of training and competition, which results in high economic and personal cost [13,14].

Spain has witnessed great growth in rugby over the last few years and it is one of the six countries worldwide which has seen an increase in the number of actual players [15], 38,000 licences in 2020 [16]. Currently, the Spanish Senior Men's Rugby XV team holds 19th place in the national team ranking for World Rugby [17], and is considered a nation in the Tier 1 performance category below other nations included in professional rugby [18]. The

injury rate observed for players in the Spanish first division is similar to that observed for amateur rugby and below professional rugby [19].

There are no studies on the incidence of injuries in Tier 1 performance category teams like the Spanish senior national team. So, it is unknown whether the injury incidence in these players correlates with the competitive level or relates to what is observed in amateur rugby. Since studies for Spain are limited and data are contradictory, further research on the pinpointing of accurate incidence rates is necessary to tailor effective injury prevention strategies [19,20]. Furthermore, these international players have access to medical attention all day every day during competition and this would mean more accurate injury diagnosis, unlike national league training, where there is no medical attention during the sessions. It is, therefore, likely that said incidence is similar to that found in younger players and depends on the level of competition. It would be interesting to see if senior players present a higher injury rate while competing at the international level than while competing at the national level, and to study whether this incidence rate comes closer to that of professional rugby or is more akin to non-professional rugby. The aim of this research is to study the incidence rate of injury in the Spanish Men's Senior National Rugby XV team and identify the most common injuries and game actions that cause them in order to develop strategies to minimize risk of injury in rugby.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1. Study Design

A longitudinal prospective cohort study with level of evidence 2b [21] was conducted. It was approved by the ethics committee of Hospital Clínico San Carlos (HREC REF: 23/504-E).

2.2. Participants

The inclusion criterion for the study was to be a member of the Spanish Senior Men's Rugby XV team during their participation in the Nations Cup Championship. National team members who were not participants in the competition were excluded. This study was carried out while the Spanish national senior team participated in the championship, organized by World Rugby over four consecutive years.

Every year, the national team gathers 10 days before the first competition match. During the competition, three competition matches are played over a ten-day period with a match every 4 days. Over a 4-year period, 72 different players took part in the competitions, 27 each consecutive year. Each player's age, height, body mass, and playing position was registered in each competition. All these 72 players were in an optimal state of health when they first joined the national team. All these players participated in this study of their own free will, signing informed consent beforehand. Each player was individually informed about the aims of this study, the steps of the investigation, and the methodology used to collect data.

2.3. Data Gathering

The national team doctor registered all injuries sustained by players during championship training sessions and matches. The diagnoses were made by a qualified medical doctor through a process of first anamnesis and physical examination, followed by imaging techniques such as X-ray, ultrasound, and magnetic resonance imaging (MRI), depending on the injury type. Through direct contact with the player, contact with the rugby club doctor and medical insurance reports, the injured players were monitored until they had fully recovered. The World Rugby consensus, created by Fuller et al. [22], was used to record injuries.

2.4. Variables

A primary injury was defined as any injury that stops a player from completing a full training session or playing in a match for more than 24 h after the injury. A recurring injury

was defined as any injury of the same type or in the same body part as a previous injury, received when the player goes back to fully competing after recovery from said injury. The severity of each injury was defined by the number of days it took the player to fully recover. Full recovery was defined as the player's physical ability to complete a scheduled training session as normal, or the physical ability to play a scheduled match. A minimum injury recovery period was stipulated as between 2 and 3 days, a slight injury recovery period between 4 and 7 days, a moderate injury recovery period between 8 and 28 days, and a severe injury recovery period, more than 28 days [22].

Each injury was noted on a record sheet containing the following information: date of injury, date of return to normal training and competition, use of protective gear, playing position, where the injury was located on the body, injury type, and the Orchard code for the classification of sports injuries [23], whether or not it was a contact injury, whether or not it was a recurring injury, whether the injury was sustained during a training session or a match, the exact situation it happened in, the exact time it happened, whether or not it was a foul and if so, whether it was sanctioned accordingly, the playing surface, and complementary diagnostic procedures and treatment. The national team doctor was responsible for compiling and registering this data on an Excel spreadsheet (Microsoft Corp, Redmond, WA, USA), adapted from Fuller et al. [22]. The minutes spent training, training mode, and the number of matches played were also registered in keeping with the World Rugby guide [24]. The calculation of matches played was reached based on 15 players (8 forwards and 7 backs) playing 80 min per match. The training time was calculated based on the sum of the different training activities in each session and the number of players taking part in each one.

2.5. Statistical Analysis

The statistical analysis was conducted using SPSS v.25 software for Windows (IBM SPSS: Statistical Package for Social Science, Chicago, IL, USA). The analysis of the variables was expressed in means and standard deviations (SD) and their 95% confidence intervals (CI). The normality of the data was analysed using the Kolmogorov–Smirnov test. The differences of means were analysed with parametric or non-parametric tests depending on the data normality results. The incidence of injuries during matches and training was recorded as the number of injuries per 1000 (ph) with a 95% confidence interval (95% CI). Injury burden is presented (mean severity \times incidence/1000 ph = days absent/1000 ph) to show the overall cost of injuries to the team in terms of days absent from a given period of exposure. The associations between qualitative variables were analysed with chi-squared comparisons. The significance level was set at $p < 0.05$.

3. Results

This section may be divided by subheadings. It should provide a concise and precise description of the experimental results, their interpretation, as well as the experimental conclusions that can be drawn.

The mean age of the players was 25.5 ± 4.07 years old. Their mean body mass was 101.5 ± 15.1 kg, and their mean height 182 ± 6.6 cm. Exposure to the game was calculated at 240 h per player during the matches and 2550 h per player during the training sessions. A total of 27 injuries were recorded. The incidence of injury was higher during matches (100.0 [95% CI: 62.0–132.9] per 1000 ph for matches compared to 1.17 [95% CI: 0–2.5] by 1000 ph for training sessions). The rate of injury sustained was higher for matches (2480 [95% CI: 1933.6–3026.3] days of absence per 1000 ph for matches) than during training sessions (18.8 [95% CI: 13.5–24.0] days of absence per 1000 ph for training sessions).

The mean days of absence caused by injury during matches was 24.7 (95% CI: 16.5–33.0), 25.1 (95% CI: 13.6–36.7) for forwards, and 24.0 (95% CI: 10.8–37.1) for backs (see Table 1). In terms of injury severity, all injuries registered caused at least 3 days of absence from the matches. The highest incidence was reported in moderate and severe injuries, 41.6 (95% CI: 16.3–66.9) injuries per 1000 ph. Severe injuries caused 1750.0 (95% CI: 1269.2–2230.7) days

of absence per 1000 ph, moderate injuries, 616.6 (95% CI: 555.1–678.1), and slight injuries, 111.6 (95% CI: 71.8–151.5) days of absence per 1000 ph.

Table 1. The number of injuries, incidence of injuries (per 1000 player-hours: 95% CI) for all injuries, match injuries and training injuries by severity (days-absence) and positions.

Match					
	Number (%)		Incidence	Severity Days-Absence Mean (95% CI)	Injury Burden
Minimal (2–3)	0		0	0	0
Forwards	0		0	0	0
Backs	0		0	0	0
Mild (4–7)	4 (16.7)		16.6 (0.47–32.8)	6.7 (5.9–7.5)	111.6 (71.8–151.5)
Forwards	2 (8.3)				
Backs	2 (8.3)				
Moderate (8–28)	10 (41.7)		41.6(16.3–66.9)	14.8 (10.2–19.3)	616.6 (555.1–678.1)
Forwards	8(33.4)				
Backs	2 (8.3)				
Severe (>28)	10 (41.7)		41.6(16.3–66.9)	42.0 (28.6–55.3)	1750.0 (1269.2–2230.7)
Forwards	6(25.0)				
Backs	4 (16.7)				
All	24 (100)	p^\dagger	100.0 (62.0–137.9)	24.7 (16.5–33.0)	2470.0 (1924.3–3015.6)
Forwards	16 (66.6)	0.102	66.6 (35.1–98.2)	25.1 (13.6–36.7)	1673.3 (1201.0–2145.5)
Backs	8 (33.4)		33.3 (10.6–56.0)	24.0 (10.8–37.1)	800.0 (456.7–1143.2)
Training					
All/ Number (proportion)	Minimal (2–3) Number (%)		Mild (4–7) Number (%)	Moderate (8–28) Number (%)	Severe (>28) Number (%)
3 (100)	1 (33.3)		0	1 (33.3)	1 (33.3)

[†] Chi-square test was used * Student’s *t*-test was used.

The most common injuries were muscular injuries and concussion, with a rate of 41.6 (95% CI: 16.3–66.9) and 29.1 (95% CI: 7.8–50.4) per 1000 ph, respectively (see Table 2). The highest incidence was for muscular injuries with 1129.1 (95% CI: 728.7–1529.5) lost days per 1000 ph. Fractures followed with an incidence of 566.6 (95% CI: 503.9–629.3) lost days per 1000 ph. The head was most injured at 33.3%, followed by the hand, the anterior thigh, and the leg, amounting to 12.5 % (see Table 3). Game actions like tackling produced most injuries, 50.0 (95% CI: 22.4–77.5) injuries per 1000 ph. Tackling also represented the greatest injury burden with 1120.0 (95% CI: 721.0–1518.9) days of absence from training and competition (see Table 4).

Table 2. Match injuries as a function of injury type and playing position.

Injury Type	Match			Incidence (95% CI)	Severity Days-Absence Mean (DS)	Injury Burden (95% CI)
	Forwards	Backs	n (%)			
Concussion	5	2	7 (29.2)	29.1 (7.8–50.4)	11.8 (±5.8)	344.1 (284.0–404.2)
Dislocation/subluxation			0	0	0	0
Sprain/ligament injury	4	1	5 (20.8)	20.8 (2.7–38.9)	21.0 (±13.2)	437.5 (374.7–500.2)
Fracture	1	1	2 (8.3)	8.3 (0–19.8)	68.0 (±33.9)	566.6 (503.9–629.3)
Other bone injuries			0	0	0	0
Lesion of meniscus, cartilage or disc			0	0	0	0
Muscle tear/strain/cramps	6	4	10 (41.7)	41.6 (16.3–66.9)	27.1 (±13.6)	1129.1 (728.7–1529.5)
Tendon rupture/tendinopathy/bursitis			0	0	0	
Haematoma/contusion/bruise			0	0	0	
All	16	8	24	100.0 (62.0–137.9)	24.7 (±19.5)	2480.0 (1933.6–3026.3)

The period in the match where most injuries occurred was during the second quarter, followed by the fourth and third quarters (see Table 5). Of injured players, 54.2% were taken off and substituted immediately. Player substitution was delayed for 37.5% of the players and 8.3% of them were not substituted at all. There was a delay in player substitution in 44.4% of cases involving muscular injury and in 42.9% of players suffering from concussion. Of players suffering from concussion, 28.6% were not diagnosed until after the match had finished. Players who kicked off the match sustained more injuries (91.6%) compared to substitute players (8.4%) ($p < 0.001$).

Table 4. Events associated with match injuries.

Events		n (%)	Incidence Injury (95% CI)	Injury Burden (95% CI)
Tackle	Being Tackle	7 (29.2)	50.0 (22.4–77.5)	1120.0 (721.0–1518.9)
	Tackling	5 (20)		
Maul		2 (8.3)	8.3 (0–19.8)	158.3 (112.1–204.5)
Ruck		4(16.7)	16.7 (0.47–32.8)	520.0 (456.7–583.2)
Scrum		1 (4.2)	4.2 (0–12.3)	58.3 (28.6–87.9)
Collision		4 (16.7)	16.7 (0.47–32.8)	441.6 (378.8–504.4)
Otros		1 (4.2)	4.2 (0–12.3)	183.3 (134.3–232.2)
Total		24 (100)	100.0 (62.0–137.9)	2480.0 (1933.6–3026.3)

Table 5. Injuries by match quarter and substitution.

Match Quarter	n (%)	Incidence Injury (95% CI)	Injury Burden (95% CI)	Days-Lost Mean (DS)
First Quarter	3 (12.5)	12.5 (0–26.5)	607.5 (545.7–669.2)	48.6 (±41.1)
Second Quarter	8 (33.3)	33.3 (10.6–56.0)	733.3 (677.3–789.2)	22.0 (±12.9)
Third Quarter	6 (25.0)	25.0 (5.2–44.7)	595.0 (532.8–657.1)	23.8 (±12.8)
Fourth Quarter	7 (29.2)	29.2 (7.8–50.4)	539.5 (476.5–602.6)	18.5 (±14.8)
Substitution	n (%)	Incidence injury (95% CI)	Injury Burden (95% CI)	Days-lost Mean (SD)
No substitution	2 (8.3)	8.3 (0–19.8)	79.1 (45.0–113.3)	9.5 (±3.5)
Inmediate substitution	13 (54.2)	54.2 (25.5–82.2)	1841.6 (1351.2– 2332.0)	34.0 (±21.2)
Delayed substitution	9 (37.5)	37.5 (13.4–61.5)	551.2 (488.3–614.1)	14.7 (±10.3)

4. Discussion

This is the first epidemiological study on injuries sustained by the players of a Tier 1 performance category level like the Spanish Men's Senior National Rugby XV team during international competition. Most injuries occurred in competition matches with 100 injuries per each 1000 ph. These results are similar to those reported in professional rugby, varying between 79.4 injuries per 1000 ph in the World Cup 2019 [25], 87 injuries per 1000 ph in the English Premiership [9], and 241 injuries per 1000 ph in Super Rugby South African Team [5], or in semi-professional rugby in teams from Wales, with an incidence of 99.8 injuries per 1000 ph [26]. These results are higher than those found in amateur or junior rugby, where the injury rate lies between 23.7 and 46.8 injuries per 1000 ph [3,8]. They are also similar to injuries reported for the Spanish under 18's and under 20's [20]. Yet even

though we are dealing with the same population, the incidence of injury in international competition is higher than that reported for Spanish national competition [19]. These differences may arise because of the higher competitive level in international competition. Previous studies have demonstrated this association between the level of competition and a higher incidence of injury [2,27], and we have corroborated this data in this study. Although the level of competition related to a higher incidence of injury in women has not been observed [28], this difference may be explained by physical differences between the sexes. Men's larger body mass and speed in tackling allows for more energy in contact.

In this study, we have found a higher injury rate when the national team players take part in international competition than when they take part in the national league. The intensity of training is different for international competition to that of national competition. Matches are played every 4 days in international competition, whereas they are played every 6 to 7 days in national competition. Previous studies show an increase in the risk of injury when training intensity is suddenly increased [29], making it advisable to adequately control training intensity at the rugby club level to later adapt the individual to the training intensity required when playing for the national team. Better communication between club technicians and national team technicians would be beneficial in minimizing risk factors that cause injury in players who compete internationally. The fact that international players have matches every 4 days means a high number of tackles in a shorter period of time, which affects the ability of the player to maintain those higher energy levels and increases the possibility of muscular damage as indicated by Hendriks and Lambert [30]. On average, the days lost because of injury are similar to those observed for professional or semi-professional rugby players [9,26] but less than those reported in research on amateur players or for elite Spanish rugby competition [3,19]. These differences may be explained by the fact that elite rugby teams always have a medical service on hand. This allows for earlier diagnosis and treatment, which may reduce the number of days lost; it also makes the recording of injuries easier, which may explain this higher incidence rate [31].

Muscular injuries were most common, which coincides with findings reported in research on professional rugby [7,32] or in previous studies on players in elite Spanish rugby competition [19]. Concussion was reported at a similar incidence rate to that reported in recent research on professional rugby in Wales, 15.3 cases of concussion per 1000 ph [4] or 15.4 cases of concussion per 1000 ph in the 2019 World Cup [25]. It was, however, reported at a higher incidence rate than that reported in elite Spanish rugby competition, 4.8 cases of concussion per 1000 ph [19], or in community rugby, less than 4 cases of concussion per 1000 ph [3]. An increase in the incidence of concussion has been observed in professional rugby since 2011, which may be due to enhanced medical knowledge of the injury and the use of more precise diagnostic tools [9]. We carried out this study in competitive rugby using The Head Injury Assessment (HIA) protocol, which seeks to improve the diagnosis for concussion in elite rugby [33]. In keeping with other studies [34,35], we found that although it may have been possible to temporarily substitute players who are suspected of having concussion and assess them to that end, 28% of concussion diagnoses were made after the match. The national league teams do not have access to medical attention during most of their training sessions. Nor do they have access to technical assistance (video imaging) as recommended by World Rugby in international matches, which would help in the diagnosis of concussion both during and after the matches. We recommend that national league teams have access to both video imaging tools to enable medical staff to better analyse injury, and daily medical attention. If these measures were in place, the rate of concussion diagnoses would possibly increase in this population, thereby minimizing the consequences on the one hand and avoiding bias in epidemiological studies on the other.

Tackling was the game action that produced most injuries, with the tackled player sustaining the most injuries. This is similar to findings for professional rugby or community rugby [3,32]. All previous studies coincide in that tackling is the game action that presents the most risk of injury, although some authors indicate that this risk may be related to the greater frequency of this action more than the contact involved [36]. In this study, we

report the most frequent injuries in players kicking off the match, which may be related to levels of player fatigue. This would then correspond with more game time as opposed to a higher frequency of tackling actions. It has been shown that the tackling technique diminishes with both physical and mental fatigue [37,38]. We would recommend future studies to relate levels of fatigue during the matches with the number of tackles the player engages in and the consequent injuries sustained.

Since this study was carried out on players in the Spanish Men's Senior National Rugby XV team, results cannot be extrapolated to the rest of the national teams. It would be interesting to assess the incidence of injury in other national teams similar to the Spanish national team and ascertain the association of accumulated fatigue in the tackling action with game time, in order to corroborate the findings of this study.

5. Conclusions

Injuries are more frequent during the Spanish Men's Senior National Rugby XV team matches, with an incidence of 100 injuries per 1000 ph. Muscular injuries and concussion are the most frequent injuries and tackling is the game action that produces most of these injuries. Players who kick off the match sustain more injuries compared to those who go on later as substitutes. Since 28% of concussion cases are diagnosed after the match, we recommend continued research on diagnostic tool improvement to be able to detect cases of concussion during the match. Finally, we recommend the insistence on training tackling techniques, while developing and implementing objective methods to quantify fatigue during training sessions.

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Data Availability Statement: The data presented in this study are available on request from the corresponding author. The data are not publicly available due to privacy.

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